

Appendix Selected Studies

No.	Author	Title	Jurnal	Tahun	Country Setting
1.	Olabe, JC; Olabe, MA; Basogain, X; (Olabe et al. 201)	Programming and robotics with Scratch in primary education	Education in a technological world	2014	USA
2.	Lye, SY; Koh, JHL(Sze Yee Lye and Koh 2018)	Review on teaching and learning of computational thinking through programming: What is next for K-12?	Computers in human behavior	2014	Singapore
3.	Kalelioğlu, F; Gülbahar, Y; Akçay, S; (Kalelioğlu et al. 2014)	Curriculum integration ideas for improving the computational thinking skills of learners through programming via scratch	Local Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Informatics in Schools: Situation, Evolution and Perspectives ISSEP 2014	2014	Turkey
4.	Sáez-López, José-Manuel; González, Marcos Román; Vázquez-Cano, Esteban(Sáez-López, Román-González, and Vázquez-Cano 2016)	Visual programming languages integrated across the curriculum in elementary school: A two year case study using “Scratch” in five schools	Computers & Education	2016	Spain
5.	OLUK, Ali; KORKMAZ, Özgen(OLUK and KORKMAZ 2016)	Comparing Students’ Scratch Skills with Their Computational Thinking Skills in Terms of Different Variables	International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science	2016	Turkey
6.	Oluk, A; Korkmaz, Ö(Oluk and Korkmaz 2016)	Comparing Students' Scratch Skills with Their Computational Thinking Skills in Terms of Different Variables.	Modern Education and computer science	2016	Turkey
7.	Flórez, Francisco Buitrago; Casallas, Rubby; Hernández, Mario; Reyes, Alejandro; Restrepo, Silvia; Danies, Giovanna(Flórez et al. 2017)	Changing a Generation’s Way of Thinking: Teaching Computational Thinking Through Programming	Review of Educational Research : Sage Journal	2017	Columbia
8.	Moreno-León, J; Robles, G;(Moreno-León, Robles, and ... 2017)	Towards data-driven learning paths to develop computational thinking with scratch	IEEE Transactions on emergine topics in computing	2017	Spain
9.	Rose, S; Habgood, J; Jay, T(Rose 2019)	An exploration of the role of visual programming tools in the development of young children's computational thinking	Electronic journal of e-learning	2017	North england
10.	Brackmann, CP; Román-González, M; Robles, G;(Brackmann et al. 2017)	Development of computational thinking skills through unplugged activities in primary school	Proceedings of 12th Workshop in Primary and Secondary Computing Education	2017	Spain
11.	Lye, Sze Yee; Koh, Joyce Hwee Ling(Sze Yee Lye and Koh 2018)	Case Studies of Elementary Children’s Engagement in Computational Thinking Through Scratch Programming	Computational Thinking in the STEM Disciplines	2018	Singapore
12.	Vinayakumar, R; Soman, KP; Menon, Pradeep(Vinayakumar, Soman, and Menon 2018)	Fractal Geometry: Enhancing Computational Thinking with MIT Scratch	International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)	2018	India
13.	Hassan, Haslina; Adnan, Aliza; Poh, Lye Guet; Hashim, Mohd Saferi Mohd(Hassan et al. 2018)	Using Scratch Programming To Engage Primary School Pupils In Computational Thinking	Jurnal Penyelidikan TEMPAWAN	2018	Malaysia
14.	Harimurti, Rina; Qoiriah, Anita; Ekohariadi, Ekohariadi; Munoto, Munoto(Harimurti et al. 2018)	Implementation of Computational Thinking Concepts in ICT Learning Using Scratch Programming	Proceedings of the International Conference on Indonesian Technical Vocational Education and Association (APTEKINDO 2018)	2018	Indonesia
15.	Šerbec, IN; Cerar, Š; Žerovnik, A(Šerbec, Cerar, and Žerovnik 2018)	Developing computational thinking through games in scratch	Education and Research	2018	Slovenia
16.	Katchapakirin, K; Anutariya, C(Katchapakirin and Anutariya 2018)	An architectural design of scratchthai: A conversational agent for computational thinking development using scratch	The 10th International Conference on Advances in Information Technology (IAIT2018)	2018	Thailand
17.	Liu, Yaqin; Ma, Zhiqiang; Qian, Yizhou(Liu, Ma, and Qian 2019)	Developing Chinese Elementary School Students' Computational Thinking	Proceedings of the ACM Conference on Global Computing Education	2019	China
18.	Rose, S(Rose 2019)	Developing children's computational thinking using programming games	ProQuest LLC	2019	UK
19.	Park, Youngki; Shin, Youhyun(Park and Shin 2019)	Comparing the Effectiveness of Scratch and App Inventor with Regard to Learning Computational Thinking Concepts	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	2019	Korea
20.	Troiano, GM; Snodgrass, S; Argimak, E; (Troiano et al. 2019)	Is my game OK Dr. Scratch? Exploring programming and computational thinking development via metrics in student-designed serious games for STEM	Proceedings of the 18th ACM International Conference on Interaction Design and Children	2019	USA
21.	Angeli, C; Giannakos, M (Angeli and Giannakos 2020)	Computational thinking education: Issues and challenges	Computers in human behavior	2020	Cyprus
22.	Pérez-Marín, D; Hijón-Neira, R; Bacelo, A; (Pérez-Marín et al. 2020)	Can computational thinking be improved by using a methodology based on metaphors and scratch to teach computer programming to children?	Computers in Human Behavior	2020	Finland

23.	Rodríguez-Martínez, JA; (Rodríguez-Martínez and ... 2020)	Computational thinking and mathematics using Scratch: an experiment with sixth-grade students	Interactive Learning environments, Routledge	2020	Spain
24.	Fagerlund, J(J Fagerlund 2021)	Teaching, learning and assessing computational thinking through programming with Scratch in primary schools	JYU dissertations	2021	Finland
25.	Mukasheva, M; Omirzakova, A(Mukasheva and Omirzakova 2021)	Computational Thinking Assessment at Primary School in the Context of Learning Programming.	World Journal on Educational Technology	2021	Khazakhstan
26.	Jiang, Bo; Li, Zhixuan(Jiang and Li 2021)	Effect of Scratch on computational thinking skills of Chinese primary school students	Journal of Computers in Education	2021	China
27.	Wei, Xuefeng; Lin, Lin; Meng, Nanxi; Tan, Wei; Kong, Siu-Cheung; Kinshuk(Wei et al. 2021)	The effectiveness of partial pair programming on elementary school students' Computational Thinking skills and self-efficacy	Computers & Education	2021	China
28.	Relkin, E; Ruitter, LE de; Bers, MU(E Relkin, Ruitter, and Bers 2021)	Learning to code and the acquisition of computational thinking by young children	Computers & education	2021	USA
29.	Fagerlund, Janne; Vesisenaho, Mikko; Häkkinen, Päivi(Janne Fagerlund, Vesisenaho, and Häkkinen 2022)	Fourth grade students' computational thinking in pair programming with Scratch: A holistic case analysis	International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction	2022	Finland
30.	Piedade, João; Dorotea, Nuno(Piedade and Dorotea 2022)	Effects of Scratch-based activities on 4th-grade students' computational thinking skills	International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction	2022	Portugal
31.	Wang, Xiao; Yin, Ya-lin(Wang and Yin 2023)	Research on Scratch Programming Teaching Design for the Cultivation of Computational Thinking	Advanced Journal of Engineering	2023	China
32.	Koray, Abdullah; Bilgin, Eda(Koray and Bilgin 2023)	The Effect of Block Coding (Scratch) Activities Integrated into the 5E Learning Model in Science Teaching on Students' Computational Thinking Skills and Programming Self-Efficacy	Science Insights Education Frontiers	2023	Turkey
33.	Relkin, Emily(Emily Relkin 2025)	The Effects of Three Coding Educational Interventions on Young Childrens Computational Thinking Skills	AERA 2024	2024	USA
34.	Grover, Shuchi; Pea, Roy (2025)	Computational Thinking and Artificial Intelligence in K- 12 Education: Emerging Synergies and Pedagogical Implications	Computers and Education	2025	USA
35.	: Bers, Marina Umaschi; Sullivan, Amanda (Bers Marina Sullivan 2025)	Beyond Coding: Early Childhood Computational Thinking in the Era of Artificial Intelligence	Computers in Human Behavior Reports	2025	USA